

THE QUESTION OF TEACHING STUDENT GIRLS TO SEW

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Annation: in this proverb, ideas were put forward about the peculiarity of teaching sewing in technology classes with student girls and the use of interactive techniques.

Keywords: tradition, reader, technology, lesson, inclusivity, textiles.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching student girls to sew in technology classes is a unique approach that brings various benefits to education. The integration of interactive methods has made sewing lessons more fun and enjoyable for most students. The use of interactive techniques in teaching sewing in technology classes with student Girls has many benefits. Promotion of creativity, ensuring practical skill, the formation of inclusiveness. One of the noticeable benefits of using interactive techniques when teaching student girls to sew in technology classes is promoting creativity. Interactive teaching methods give students a platform to experiment with different fabrics, patterns and designs, provoking their creativity. Students can experiment with various digital tools and applications such as CAD software and smart textiles to create unique fashion items. Freedom to be creative can adversely

affect students ' self-confidence, attitudes towards learning, and overall well-being. Teaching sewing through interactive methods also provides practical skills that students can apply outside of the classroom. Students learn to sew buttons, skirt and fix clothes, make them more independent when managing their clothes, and reduce the risk of being dependent on outside parties to deal with minor issues with their clothes. These practical skills can benefit students in their daily lives and future careers. Interactive sewing classes also shape neighborhood, giving students a safe place to research and support their personal interests. Traditionally, Sewing has been associated with women, but the use of interactive techniques in teaching sewing in technology classes ensures gender equality. Such methods stimulate inclusiveness among students, taranura diversity, ensure harmony. Students can research different fashion styles and express their individuality through sewing projects. In addition, the use of interactive methods in teaching sewing in technology classes is essential to provide an interesting and interesting learning platform. Interactive classes include activities such as digital design, virtual reality and games, making the learning process fun and fun. Students can also receive feedback from their peers and teachers, which increases the learning experience through constructive criticism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The success of the educational process depends not only on its shape, but also on the effectiveness of the methods used. In educational theory, unit (educational) methods occupy a central role. "Method" is a Greek metodos word meaning 'way, like to apply. The educational method is the joint activities of the teacher and students in the educational process aimed at achieving a specific goal. The teacher's choice of methods and methodical techniques in preparing for a new topic means balancing their mutual exchange on a time and didactic goal. Ultimately, conditions are created to ensure a high level of mental and practical activity of the learners. Properly applied methods deepen my knowledge of

objective reality and increase the scientific and theoretical level of holistic and training. Successively sorted teaching methods lead to a certain degree to the development of cognitive and professional interest , to the activation of independent practical activity. Educational methods represent ways of achieving the goals of teaching itself and ways of theoretical and practical orientation of educational material. Shooting techniques determine what the activities of the teacher and student should be in the educational process, how the teaching process should be organized and conducted, and what work actions the learners should perform in this process. Now the teacher acts not as an actor, but as a planner. Innovative methods are a theoretical and practical cognitive activity aimed at performing the reading tasks of learners with learners. The reader assumes a mediating role between the knowledge accumulated in human experience and the consciousness of a child who does not yet have this knowledge. The child cannot systematically master all the wealth of knowledge in socio-historical experience on his own without education, without a teacher, independently. The greatest service of the teacher is manifested in the determination of certain ways, methods of mastering the educational material. The method of the lesson process is a way, a way of activity aimed at outlining the educational material and getting to know it well by children. The educational process and results depend on the methods of work of the teacher, which determine the movement of students ' cognitive activity. For this reason, always in pedagogy, educational methods are considered as methods of work of the teacher and methods of cognitive activity of students, both of which are aimed at performing educational tasks. Pedagogical methods determine the nature of the activities of the teacher and students, will depend on the purpose and content of Education.

CONCLUSION

Teaching sewing in technology classes with student girls using interactive methods is a unique and modern approach that provides creativity, provides

practical skills, shapes inclusiveness, makes training fun and enjoyable. The benefits of this method cannot be underestimated, it must be encouraged more in the modern curriculum. In general, interactive methods serve as a modern approach that gives students an advanced and cheerful learning experience that prepares them for the future.

REFERENCES:

- 1.The decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 PF-4947 “on the strategy of Action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”.
- 2.Collection of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017., No. 6, p.70. - T.,2017.
- 3.Ishmukhamedov R.J. Ways to improve the efficiency of education using innovative technologies. T.2004
- 4.Ochilov M. New pedagogical technologies. Against.: Nasaf. 2000.